

IMPLEMENTATION OF DIGITAL POPULATION IDENTITY (IKD) AT THE POPULATION AND CIVIL REGISTRATION SERVICE OF EAST BOLAANG MONGONDOW REGENCY

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Abstract

This study aims to analyze the implementation of Digital Population Identity (IKD) at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency. This research employs a qualitative method with a descriptive approach. Data collection techniques were conducted through interviews, observations, and documentation. The analysis uses Edward III's policy implementation theory, which includes communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure. The results of the study indicate that the implementation of the IKD program at the Department of Population and Civil Registration of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency has been running fairly well. However, several obstacles remain, such as low levels of digital literacy among the community, limited technological devices, insufficient socialization program to the public, and internet network constraints. Therefore, it is necessary to enhance program socialization, strengthen technological infrastructure support, and improve community digital literacy so that the implementation of the IKD program can run more optimally in improving the quality of population administration services in East Bolaang Mongondow Regency.

Keyword: *Implementation, Digital Population Identity, East Bolaang Mongondow.*

INTRODUCTION

Population administration services are a form of basic service that plays a strategic role in governance and national development. Population administration encompasses the entire range of activities involved in organizing and regulating the issuance of population documents and data through population registration and civil registration. Population documents such as the Electronic Identity Card (KTP-el), Family Card (KK), birth certificates, and other civil documents serve as the primary basis for the public to access various public services, including health, education, banking, social assistance, and other public services.[1] Along with the development of information and communication technology, demands for improved quality of public services are increasing. The government is required to adapt to digital developments by implementing electronic-based service systems. This aligns with the Electronic-Based Government System (SPBE) policy, which aims to realize clean, effective, transparent, and accountable governance and improve the quality of public services. [2]Digital transformation is one of the government's main strategies to accelerate bureaucratic reform and increase the efficiency of public services, including in the field of population administration.

The Indonesian government, through the Ministry of Home Affairs, specifically the Directorate General of Population and Civil Registration (Dukcapil), continues to strive to modernize population administration to improve the quality of services for the public. One of the strategic innovations launched is the Digital Population Identity (IKD), which is a digital representation of population documents containing resident identity data in the form of an application that can be accessed via smartphone devices. With the IKD, the public is no longer completely dependent on physical documents, because population identity can be shown digitally anytime and anywhere. One of these strategic breakthroughs is in line with research stating that the implementation of public policies in the population sector must be aimed at increasing service effectiveness, accelerating processes, and expanding citizens' reach to basic services including education [3]. In this case, IKD becomes a form of official digital-based population identity that complements the e-KTP as proof of the validity of a person's identity in accordance with the Regulation of the

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Minister of Home Affairs (Permendagri) No. 72 of 2022 concerning Standards and Specifications for Hardware, Software, and Electronic Identity Card Forms and the Implementation of Digital Population Identity, the Indonesian government establishes a new regulatory framework for managing population identity that focuses on digital transformation. The implementation of the IKD is expected to provide various benefits, including accelerating service processes, reducing administrative costs, minimizing the risk of loss or damage to physical documents, increasing the accuracy of population data, and reducing the potential for identity theft. Furthermore, the IKD is also expected to improve the efficiency of population administration services, both in terms of service time, procedures, personnel, and costs incurred by the public.

However, the implementation of IKD at the regional level has not always been optimal. Various challenges remain, such as limited information technology infrastructure, internet network quality, human resource readiness, community digital literacy, and public understanding of the benefits and uses of IKD. Furthermore, social, economic, and geographic factors also influence the success of IKD implementation, particularly in regions characterized by vast territories and unequal access to technology. East Bolaang Mongondow Regency, a region in North Sulawesi Province, is implementing a Digital Population Identity (ID) policy through the Population and Civil Registration Office (Dinas Dukcapil). The implementation of IKD in this region is expected to be a solution to improve the efficiency of population administration services, which currently face various challenges, such as relatively long service processes, high reliance on physical documents, limited public access in certain areas, and frequent queues.

Data from the East Bolaang Mongondow Regency Population and Civil Registration Office (Disdukcapil) shows that the number of IKD activations has only reached 1,155 out of 59,350 people (those with ID cards), resulting in a significant gap in achievement. Many people still do not have or use IKD, either due to limited knowledge, low digital literacy, limited smartphone devices, or internet network constraints. Furthermore, service personnel still need to increase their capacity in managing the IKD system to ensure optimal service delivery. This situation indicates a gap between the policy objectives of the IKD implementation and the reality of its implementation on the ground. On the one hand, the IKD is designed as an instrument to improve the efficiency of population administration services, but on the other hand, various obstacles remain that can reduce the effectiveness and efficiency of the expected services. Therefore, an in-depth study is needed on how the IKD implementation is carried out, how it contributes to service efficiency, and what factors influence its success and obstacles in implementation.

Thus, based on the background description above, research on the implementation of Digital Population Identity (IKD) at the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency is very important to conduct. This research is expected to provide a comprehensive overview of the role of IKD in improving service efficiency, and can serve as evaluation material and recommendations for local governments in order to realize more effective, efficient, and digital-based population administration services in the future.

METHOD

This study uses a qualitative research approach with a descriptive method. The qualitative approach is used to understand in depth the phenomenon of the implementation of the Digital Population Identity (IKD) policy at the Population and Civil Registration Service of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency. According to Sugiyono in Pasolong, [4], [5], [6] qualitative research is a research method used to examine the conditions of natural objects, as opposed to experiments, where researchers are key instruments. The qualitative approach allows researchers to explore the experiences, perceptions, and views of informants who are directly involved in the implementation of IKD, both from the side of service providers and the user community.

This approach was chosen because the phenomena being studied are contextual, complex, and require a holistic understanding. IKD implementation is not only related to technical aspects, but also relates to human resource readiness, infrastructure, work culture, data security, and community response. Therefore, a qualitative approach allows researchers to:

1. Examine the IKD implementation process in depth, including the dynamics and challenges faced in population administration services.
2. Exploring the meaning and perceptions of informants, such as Civil Registration Service employees, IKD operators, and community users regarding the ease, speed, accuracy, and security of IKD services.
3. Understanding the relationship between IKD and service efficiency through detailed narrative descriptions and based on empirical field data.
4. Produce contextual findings that can provide concrete recommendations for improving services at the Civil Registration Office.

The qualitative descriptive approach in this study was used to systematically and in-depth describe the implementation process of the Digital Population Identity (IKD) policy at the Population and Civil Registration

Service of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency.

This study focuses on the implementation of Digital Population Identity (IKD) at the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency, using Edward III's (1980) policy implementation theory. This policy implementation model emphasizes four important variables that influence the success of a policy's implementation:

1. Communication
2. Resource
3. Disposition (Attitude of the Executor)
4. Bureaucratic Structure

These four variables are the focus of research to analyze how the Digital Population Identity policy is implemented in population administration services at the Population and Civil Registration Service of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency.

Apart from the researcher as the main instrument, this study also uses several supporting instruments, namely: interview guidelines, observation sheets and documentation instruments. Data sources were obtained from several informants involved in the implementation of IKD in Dukcapil of East Bolmong Regency such as: Officials/employees of the Dukcapil Office of East Bolmong and community users of IKD services. This study uses several data collection techniques, namely: Observation, Interviews and Documentation. The data analysis technique used in this study refers to the interactive analysis model of Miles, Huberman, and Saldaña, which consists of several stages, namely: Data collection, Data reduction, Data presentation and drawing conclusions and verification. Meanwhile, for data validity, credibility techniques (credibility), transferability, dependability, and confirmability were used.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Communication

Communication is a crucial factor in the successful implementation of public policy. According to Edward III in Kairupan (2013), communication in policy implementation is not only concerned with conveying information to implementers but also to the public as the policy's target group [6]. Effective communication is necessary to ensure that the objectives, content, and implementation procedures are clearly understood by all parties involved. In the context of implementing the Digital Population Identity (IKD) program, communication is crucial because this program represents a relatively new digital population administration service innovation for the public. Therefore, providing clear information regarding the purpose, benefits, and how to use the IKD application is essential for the public to understand and utilize the service effectively. Based on the results of research conducted at the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency, it was found that the communication process related to the Digital Population Identity (IKD) program has been carried out by officials through various forms of information delivery to the public. One form of communication carried out is through direct outreach to the public who come to process population administration documents at the Population and Civil Registration Office. This condition is in line with the view of Edward III (1980) who stated that the success of policy implementation is greatly influenced by the effectiveness of communication, especially in terms of delivering information to target groups. Direct communication is considered capable of increasing public understanding due to the two-way interaction between officials and the public.

During the service, officers explained the Digital Population Identity program, including the benefits of using the IKD application and how to activate the application on people's smartphones. Furthermore, officers provided assistance to residents experiencing difficulties activating the IKD application. Public involvement through participatory communication is a crucial factor in increasing acceptance of public policy.[7] However, the research also found that the communication process regarding the Digital Population Identity (IKD) program to the public has not been optimal. This is indicated by the fact that some people still do not receive information about the IKD program before accessing services at the Population and Civil Registration Office. One informant from the community who uses the service stated that he only learned about the IKD program when he went directly to the Dukcapil office to process population documents. This situation indicates that the dissemination of policy information has not reached the entire community evenly. From the perspective of policy implementation theory, this situation indicates that the communication dimension has not been functioning effectively. According to Edward III, policy communication encompasses three main aspects: transmission, clarity, and consistency of messages. If policy information is not conveyed effectively to the public, it will create a gap in understanding, which will impact low levels of public participation in the program.[8] The findings of this study also align with the views of Van Meter and Van Horn, who stated that inter-organizational communication and the delivery of information to target groups (the public) are crucial

factors in ensuring successful policy implementation [9]. A lack of effective communication can lead to information distorts and hinder the achievement of policy objectives. Therefore, communication regarding the Digital Population Identity program still needs to be improved, particularly in terms of disseminating information to the wider public. More intensive outreach can be conducted through various communication channels, such as utilizing social media, community outreach at the sub-district and village levels, and collaborating with village governments to disseminate information about the IKD program to the public. With more effective communication, it is hoped that the public will better understand the benefits and procedures for using the Digital Population Identity application so that the implementation of the program can run more optimally in improving the quality of population administration services [10].

Resource

Resources are a crucial factor in determining the success of public policy implementation. According to Edward III, resources are all forms of capabilities possessed by the policy-implementing organization, including human resources, facilities and infrastructure, and the technological support necessary for policy implementation. Without adequate resources, a well-formulated policy will not be implemented optimally.[8] Based on the results of observations and interviews conducted, it is known that the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency has several resources to support the implementation of the IKD program. One important resource in the implementation of this program is human resources tasked with providing population administration services to the public. IKD service officers/Operators play a crucial role in the IKD application activation process and provide assistance to people experiencing difficulties in using the application. They also provide explanations regarding the benefits and how to use the IKD application to the public.[11]

In addition to human resources, the implementation of the IKD program at the Dukcapil Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency has also been supported by the availability of facilities and infrastructure used in population administration services. These facilities and infrastructure include computers/laptops for data recording and verification, network systems and servers for the Population Administration Information System (SIAK), IKD service rooms, and internet networks used in the service process to the public. This condition is in line with the view of Edward III (1980) who stated that the availability of facilities and infrastructure is a critical factor in determining the success of policy implementation. With the availability of adequate facilities, program implementation can run more effectively, efficiently, and is able to support improvements in the quality of public services.[12]

However, based on field research results, it was also found that the implementation of the IKD program still faces several obstacles related to resources. One of the obstacles faced is the limited number of service personnel handling the IKD application activation process. This condition results in a fairly high workload for officers, especially when the public comes simultaneously to access population administration services at the Dukcapil Office. This situation is in line with Edward III's view, which emphasizes that limited human resources can hinder the effectiveness of policy implementation. [8]Therefore, an imbalance between the number of officers and the volume of services has the potential to reduce service quality, such as increasing waiting times and reducing the optimization of services to the community.

Furthermore, another resource-related constraint is the quality of the internet network, which sometimes experiences disruptions or instability. Given that the IKD application activation process relies heavily on the internet network system, unstable network conditions can impact the smooth delivery of public services. This aligns with Edward III's perspective, which emphasizes that the availability and reliability of technological resources are crucial for successful policy implementation. Therefore, inadequate network infrastructure can result in suboptimal service delivery and potentially delays in the completion of population administration services [13]. Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the resources available at the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency have generally supported the implementation of the Digital Population Identity program. However, there is still a need to increase the number of service personnel and strengthen the technological infrastructure to support the smooth operation of digital-based population administration services.

Disposition

According to Edward III, disposition relates to the attitude, commitment, and willingness of implementing officials to implement established policies. A positive attitude toward a policy will encourage its successful implementation, while a less supportive attitude can hinder its implementation.[8] Based on the research conducted, it was found that the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency demonstrated a positive attitude toward the implementation of the Digital Population Identity (IKD) program. This attitude was reflected in the implementing officials' commitment to providing optimal service to the public and their willingness

to assist the public in the IKD application activation process. This supportive attitude demonstrated the officials' commitment to ensuring the success of the IKD program in the field. Service personnel also demonstrated a high level of responsiveness to members of the public experiencing difficulties using the IKD application. This was evident in the active role of officers, who not only provided explanations regarding application procedures but also provided direct assistance to the public during the activation process. This assistance reflected the officers' concern and responsibility in ensuring the public could optimally access services. This aligns with Moenir's (2022) opinion, which states that the success of public services is greatly influenced by the attitudes and behaviors of officers, who are required to demonstrate responsibility, sincerity, and a focus on public satisfaction. A friendly, responsive, and helpful attitude from officers will improve service quality and facilitate public access.

Furthermore, implementing officials also demonstrated an open attitude toward digital-based public service innovation. This is evident in their efforts to support the implementation of the IKD program as part of the digital transformation of population administration services. This aligns with Edward III's (1980) theory, which emphasizes that the success of policy implementation is greatly influenced by the level of acceptance and support of the implementers. An open attitude toward innovation demonstrates that officials not only accept but also actively support IKD policies, thereby strengthening the success of their implementation in the field.

However, in its implementation, service personnel still face several obstacles, such as low levels of digital literacy and limited access to technological devices (smartphones) among some. These conditions require service personnel to provide more intensive assistance to the public in using the IKD application. Nevertheless, service officials continue to strive to provide optimal service to the public in accordance with their duties and responsibilities. Their positive attitude in implementing the IKD program demonstrates the commitment of policy implementers to supporting its successful implementation [8]. Thus, based on the research results, it can be concluded that the disposition or attitude of implementers in implementing the Digital Population Identity program at the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency is generally quite good. Implementing officials demonstrate a supportive attitude towards the implementation of the IKD program and are committed to providing optimal service to the community.

Bureaucratic Structure

According to Edward III, bureaucratic structure relates to how policy-implementing organizations are organized, including the division of tasks, authority, and work procedures used in policy implementation [8]. A clear and well-organized bureaucratic structure will facilitate the policy implementation process because each policy implementer has clear duties and responsibilities. Furthermore, Edward III emphasized the importance of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) in implementing a policy. SOPs serve as guidelines for officials in carrying out their duties, ensuring that policy implementation can proceed systematically and effectively. A clear bureaucratic structure supported by sound work procedures will assist officials in providing more effective services to the public.[8]

In the context of implementing the Digital Population Identity (IKD) program at the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency, the bureaucratic structure plays a crucial role in supporting its implementation. The IKD program is a policy issued by the central government through the Directorate General of Population and Civil Registration of the Ministry of Home Affairs. Therefore, its implementation at the regional level must adhere to guidelines and procedures established by the central government.[14] Based on research findings, the implementation of the Digital Population Identity (IKD) program at the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency has been running in accordance with the established organizational structure and work mechanisms.

Each apparatus has specific duties and functions, such as IKD operators, service officers, and system administrators, so that the structured division of labor is able to support the smooth service process. This finding is in line with the views of Donald Van Meter and Carl Van Horn in the policy implementation model which emphasizes the importance of the characteristics of the implementing organization [9]. An organized bureaucratic structure, clear division of roles, and well-coordinated working relationships are factors that can improve the performance of policy implementation, so that policy objectives can be achieved more effectively.[15] Furthermore, the implementation of population administration services is supported by Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs), which serve as guidelines for officials in providing services to the public. These SOPs allow for a more structured and systematic service process, thereby minimizing errors.[8] Coordination between officials within the organization, particularly within the Population and Civil Registration Service, is also a crucial factor supporting the implementation of the IKD program. Officials involved in population administration services collaborate with each other to provide services to the public, ensuring optimal and efficient service delivery. A strong working relationship between implementers strengthens organizational synergy, enabling more effective policy implementation in the field.

Thus, based on the observations and interviews conducted, it can be concluded that the bureaucratic structure for implementing the Digital Population Identity program at the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency has generally been running well. This is evident in the clear division of tasks, the existence of Standard Operating Procedures (SOPs) that serve as guidelines for service delivery, and the good coordination between officials in implementing population administration services.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of research on the Implementation of Digital Population Identity (IKD) at the Population and Civil Registration Service of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency, which was analyzed using the policy implementation theory according to Edward III which includes aspects of communication, resources, disposition, and bureaucratic structure, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. Communication

The Digital Population Identity (IKD) program at the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency has been implemented through community outreach activities and internal communication between management and implementing staff. This outreach is conducted through direct services at the Civil Registration Office (Dukcapil) and outreach services for population administration. However, some residents remain unclear about the IKD program or how to use it.

2. Resources

The implementation of the IKD program at the Population and Civil Registration Office of East Bolaang Mongondow Regency has been supported by the availability of human resources and information technology facilities and infrastructure used in population administration services. The assigned staff have assisted the public in activating the IKD application and provided explanations on its use.

3. Disposition (Attitude of the Implementer)

The attitude of the implementing officials in the IKD program demonstrates a strong commitment to providing services to the public. Civil Registration and Civil Registration officers strive to assist the public in activating the IKD application and provide information on the benefits of using digital population identification. The responsive attitude and friendly service provided by the officials are among the factors supporting the implementation of the IKD program in East Bolaang Mongondow Regency.

4. Bureaucratic Structure

The bureaucratic structure for implementing the IKD program at the East Bolaang Mongondow Regency Population and Civil Registration Office has been running smoothly. The IKD program is implemented in accordance with the provisions and policies established by the central government through the Ministry of Home Affairs. Furthermore, standard operating procedures (SOPs) and a clear division of tasks between organizational units support the implementation of digital-based population administration services.

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